

LOW INVASIVE EXAMINATION IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF CHILDREN'S SOMATIC DISEASES THE IMPORTANCE OF METHODS

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Relevance of the problem. Children's disease-includes a number of infectious and non-infectious diseases of children's age. Pediatrics it is derived from the Greek word "paidos" which means child, "iatriya" – cure. The main task of Pediatrics is to return the child to a healthy state. Children with a diagnosis of acute respiratory infection in nosology, acute allergic conditions, acute non-hospital pneumonia, acute urinary tract infection, febrile cramps, epilepsy epistatus were hospitalized for emergency treatment in the emergency department of emergency pediatrics. Rapid diagnosis in children's disease, significant in treatment. Low-invasive examination methods, namely painless, fast, provide the opportunity for the correct diagnosis.

Check Max. Study of the axiom of low-invasive examination methods in emergency pediatric diagnostics.

Material and method. In the Department of Pediatrics of the Fergana branch of the Republican Scientific Center for emergency medical care, the Department of reception and diagnosis, the importance of low - invasive examination methods in the diagnosis of patients seen and admitted to the Department for 2020 was studied.

The result. The Fergana branch of the Republican Scientific Center for emergency medical care, the admission - diagnosis department, had 11,363 applications for a pediatrician's appointment, of which 2,346 were admitted to the pediatric department. According to nosology, acute respiratory infection 1653 (70%) , acute allergic cases 66 (2.8%) , acute extra-hospital pneumonia 110 (4.6%), acute urinary tract infection 22 (0.9%), febrile cramps 251 (10.6%), epilepsy epistatuses 12 (0.5%), bronchial asthma 11(0.4%),obstructive bronchitis 153 (6.5%), gastrointestinal dysfunction enters 32 (1.3%). Diagnosis of yukori patients the following low-invasive examination methods were used in the jacket. With the help of radioscopy,the internal structure of the lungs was examined and an accurate diagnosis was made. Chest radioscopy was performed 122 (5.2%), of which pneumonia in the lungs was detected in 100%.Right-sided bronchopneumonia 9 (0.3%), left-sided bronchopneumonia 8 (0.3%), bilateral pneumonia 79 (3.3%), focal pneumonia 4 (0.1%), sigmental pneumonia 10 (0,4%) , 12 (0,5%) the patient was suspected of having destructive pneumonia, fluid in the pleural cavity,an Ultra-examination was performed,and the diagnosis of destructive pneumonia was made when it was found that there was fluid in the pleural cavities.12 patients with epilepsy epistatus and 251 with febrile cramps were admitted to the ward, Eye tube of 248 (10.5%) patients tekshirilgan.To r curtain angiopathy was detected in 198 (8.4%),

visual nerve dimming 5 (0.2%) , visual nerve disc subatrophy 12 (0.5%) , visual nerve atrophy 4 0.1 (%), eye tube unchanged 29 (1.2%) children.

Conclusion. The use of low-invasive methods in emergency medicine is important because of the speed of the examination, high level of information, safety , the reason for the correct and rapid diagnosis. This, in turn, is a treatment that is urgently done correctly, causing the children's imagination to jump.

